

2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency: Case report

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ABSTRACT We describe a patient with 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency (MHBD), which is a rare metabolic disorder that resulted from an inborn error of isoleucine metabolism. A 7-month-old male infant with previously normal developmental milestones started with symptoms of fever, torpor and persistent metabolic acidosis during the course of a respiratory infection. The condition progressed to acute deterioration and cardiac arrest. After cardiorespiratory resuscitation, he was admitted to the Intensive Care Unit. He presented with seizure, coma, metabolic acidosis and disturbed of hydroelectrolytic and glycemic imbalance. A head CT scan showed hypodensity in basal ganglia, thalamus, dentate nuclei and mesencephalon. The diagnosis was established through the dosage of organics acids in the urine that showed increased excretion of 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyric acid. Laboratory tests, neuroimage aspects, history of parents consanguinity, report of the death of other probands and clinical evolution of the patient led to the suspicion of an inborn error of metabolism.

KEYWORDS inborn error, isoleucine, X-linked, organic aciduria

Case report

We describe a male, 7-month-old, born at Peçanha, Minas Gerais, Brazil, previously healthy and with normal developmental milestones to his age. He was admitted at the hospital in his hometown with symptoms of irritability, somnolence and fever. He received a diagnosis and treatment for severe Pneumonia associated with severe dehydration and peripheral cyanosis. At this occasion, he was treated with Oxacillin and Ceftriaxone due to a clinical and laboratory presentation suggestive of bacterial infection without signs of involvement of the central nervous system. He was readmitted at the emergency room around 24 hours after discharge with somnolence, poor suction, vomiting and respiratory distress. His condition suddenly deteriorated with cardiac arrest, so he required orotracheal intubation. Also, insulin was

initiated due to hyperglycemia. He was transferred to the Intensive Care Unit of the Hospital Infantil João Paulo II at Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais. He was comatose in mechanical ventilation and with continuous intravenous sedation. Presented hyperglycemia, metabolic acidosis, hypernatremia, hyperchloremia, hypercalcemia and hypocalcemia and presented an episode of tonic-clonic generalised seizure. Treatment was performed for hydroelectrolytic disturbance, and Phenobarbital was initiated due to seizures. The patient did not present seizures recurrence after the introduction of this drug. He also presented episodes of dysautonomia, characterized by sudoresis, tachycardia and arterial hypertension, which improved after the introduction of Clonidine and Propranolol. A head CT scan was performed and showed hypodensity at basal ganglia, thalamus, dentate nuclei and mesencephalon. (Picture 1).

By the family history, parents informed consanguinity (cousins at 2nd degree) and that the first child of the couple was dead nine-months-old with a similar health condition to the patient. They also related numerous deaths at the family during the first year of life of unknown cause. In the face of the clinical presentation and findings of neuroimage, exams were collected to investigate inborn errors of metabolism. It was also initiated empiric treatment with vitamins Levocarnitine, folic

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acid, pyridoxine, riboflavin, biotin, thiamine, Q10 coenzyme and administration of hypoproteic diet.

The patient evolved with clinical stability with the treatment. After the suspension of the continuous sedation he presented a mild improvement at the conscious level but kept poor spontaneous movements; he lost the ability of visual following, and also presented dystonia of the superior limbs and facial hypomimia. The urinary organic acids analysis showed high levels of tyglyglycine and 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl which brought the hypothesis of Ketothiolase deficiency and 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl CoA dehydrogenase deficiency. It was requested then a new urine sample that confirmed the 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency. At the present case, it was not possible to verify the presence of the specific genetic mutation due to the unavailability of this test at our service.

During his hospitalization it was possible to take the patient out of mechanical ventilation despite discrete chronic retention of CO₂ and tracheostomy. He persisted with dystonia in superior limbs, severe neuropsychomotor impairment and deglutition disorder, which lead to a gastrostomy. He also kept the autonomic dysfunction despite adequate treatment.

Discussion

The inborn errors of metabolism are singular genetic disorders characterized by biochemical defects. Individually they are considered rare, but in the group, they become pathologies of significant meaning responsible for deaths and morbidity. They can have an autosomal recessive character, autosomal dominant or X-linked patterns and the signs and symptoms are a consequence of the cumulative effect of toxic substrates, deficiency or both of them. [3]

The 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency also denoted 17beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10 (HSD10) deficiency [6] is a rare inborn error of metabolism of isoleucine and branched-chain fatty acids as first described at 2000 by Zschocke et al. [2]. It is a mitochondrial enzyme capable of metabolism of 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA to 2-methyl-acetoacetyl-CoA (picture 2). As a result of the enzymatic defect, the patient commonly presents a normal neuropsychomotor development in the first months of life followed by regression of previously acquired abilities, associated with hypotonia, seizures and motor disorders. It usually starts after a stressor event.

Men with this diagnosis have low levels of the enzyme, and in the first year of life shows a delay in the neuropsychomotor development associated to metabolic acidosis. After the sixth month of age, clinical deterioration begins with the loss of psychomotor skills and progressive neurological disorders such as visual loss, epilepsy, dystonia and spasticity. The development of cardiomyopathy is common. However, women with this deficiency may be asymptomatic or manifest mild neurological conditions such as the cognitive deficit, for example, depending on the hepatic inactivation pattern of X. [6]

Diagnosis is based on the clinical suspicion of organic aciduria associated with organic acids urinary dosage which reveals increased excretion of tyglyglycine and 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl without an equal increase of 2-methyl-acetoacetyl. Usually, acylcarnitines profile shows normal results. The neuroimaging findings reported in patients with MHBD deficiency are heterogeneous and include frontotemporal or frontoparietal cortical atrophy, occipital periventricular white

Figure 1: Head CT showing hypodensity in basal ganglia, thalamus, dentate nuclei and mesencephalon.

Figure 2: Blockage at beta-oxidation of branched-chain fatty acids due to 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency. (adapted from Zschocke et al, 2000).

matter lesion, severe cerebral atrophy and occipital infarction-like images and frontotemporal atrophy with bilateral signal abnormalities in the putamen [2]. The primary differential diagnoses are respiratory chain defects and ketothiolase deficiency. Molecular studies may identify the mutant variant and help with familial genetic counselling. The disease presents a pattern of recessive inheritance X-linked, and the involved gene is HSD17B10 placed at Xp11.2 chromosome. In comparison to other inborn metabolic disorders involved at isoleucine metabolism 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl CoA dehydrogenase deficiency patients do not have any benefits of amino acid restriction diet. [7]. As in other organic acidurias, the patient can benefit from hypoproteic diet and vitamin supplements, like L-carnitine. It has been observed that male patients described in the medical literature until now have a bad prognosis with progression to a neurodegenerative state and cardiomyopathy [1,6]. There is no curative treatment yet, and management is palliative.

Conclusion

The 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyryl CoA deficiency is a rare disease, X-linked, associated with failure at isoleucine metabolism in which symptoms begin during the first years of life. There are still only 30 case reports described at literature worldwide since the first in 2000. There is no specific treatment but it is usually adopted supportive care similar to other organic acidurias like hypoproteic diet and vitamin supplement. In the other hand, clinical suspicion and early diagnosis are fundamental to improve survival and genetic counseling.

Competing Interests

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